

Employee Performance at PT. Artefak Arkindo as Affected by Leadership, Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction

Rizki Gito Perwiro, Sri Wahyulina, Putra Buana Sakti
Magister of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business
University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

Abstract:- This study aims to examine the effect of leadership style and work motivation on employee performance mediated by job satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo. This type of research is causal associative research with a quantitative approach. Sampling using a proportional random sampling technique, namely 171 respondents taken from a total population of 300 employees of PT Artefak Arkindo. Data analysis using PLS-SEM technique with Smart PLS 3 software. The results showed that leadership style had no significant effect on employee performance. Work motivation and job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Leadership style and work motivation have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of leadership style and work motivation on employee performance.

Keywords:- Leadership Style, Work Motivation, Employee Performance, and Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) has been commonly recognized as a key strategic issue (Machado & Davim, 2018) and a source of competitive advantage for all organizations (Machado & Davim, 2018; Marchington, 2021). According to Armstrong, (2014), HR is everything related to humans in the organization, including skills, knowledge, experience, motivation, and attitudes. HR can also be interpreted as the workforce available in an organization, which consists of employees, managers, and leaders. According to Dessler, (2017), HR may also be viewed as a resource that can be created and managed to help organizations accomplish their objectives. Quality human resources may help organizations achieve goals including improving productivity, quality, and innovation. Furthermore, human resources are important individuals in organizations and businesses. To ensure that management operations in an organization operate smoothly, the firm must have knowledgeable and highly competent personnel, as well as make every effort to manage the company properly so that employee performance improves.

Performance is work achievement, which is a comparison between real work results and established standards (Dessler, 1992). According to (Robbins P, Stephen and Judge A, 2017), performance is the result achieved by a job where employees meet certain criteria that apply to the job. This can include meeting deadlines, producing quality work, or complying with company policies. From the above

statement, employee performance is seen from the work of each employee. The indicators for measuring employee performance according to (Robbins, 2010) with work quantity, work quality, timeliness, effectiveness, and independence.

Employee performance can be influenced by several factors according to Duha. (2018) namely motivation, organizational culture, leadership style, work procedures, communication, education level, work experience, compensation, training, career development, job promotion, loyalty, physical environment, organizational climate, conflict, organizational commitment, and organizational effectiveness. Anoraga (2017: 178) explains that the factors that affect performance are work motivation, training and education (competence), compensation, technology, skills, and work discipline. From the factors mentioned above, researchers want to re-examine the factors of leadership style and work motivation. Because leadership style is one of the determinants of the successful achievement of an organization. Leaders have a role to move and influence employees to improve performance so that the goals of the organization can be achieved (Sadia & Aman, 2018; Rachmaliya, 2017) cited by Setiabudi et al., (2023). Meanwhile, motivation refers to why and how a person behaves in a certain way. With the motivation that arises, it will encourage someone to do something in accordance with the expected goals (Rohmah et al., 2023). Providing the right motivation is expected to encourage employees to work in a better (Verawati et al., 2023).

Leadership style is a behavior and approach that results from a mix of philosophies, abilities, qualities, and attitudes that are frequently used by a leader and activities to persuade people to collaborate in order to accomplish the intended goals (Mahaputra, 2023). Meanwhile, leadership style according to (Rivai & Mulyadi, 2012) is a way or norm of behavior that a leader applies when he tries to influence the performance of his subordinates. Because the behavior shown by subordinates is basically the subordinates' response to the leadership style exercised on them (Ali & Agustian, 2018). The indicators for measuring leadership style according to Kartono, (2016) are the capacity to make judgments, motivate others, communicate effectively, govern subordinates, and control emotions are all important. Supported by previous research conducted by (Jayanti & Wati, 2020); (Efitriana & Liana, 2022); Gunawan et al., (2022) that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. However, it is not in line with the findings of research conducted by (Wibowo & Syafii, 2023) that leadership style

actually has no effect on employee performance. More in-depth research needs to be done because there is still a research gap related to the relationship between these variables.

Work motivation is the next element that influences employee performance. Work motivation is the drive or desire that drives someone to work hard and meet the company's goals. Employee work motivation, according to Robbins and Judge (2017), is an internal process that initiates, leads, and sustains effective and meaningful work behavior. Meanwhile, employee work motivation, according to Luthans (2011), is a psychological condition that pushes a person to execute certain behaviors aimed at specified goals. With the existence of this work motivation, employees will give their best, work more productively, and increase work effectiveness and efficiency (Muna & Isnowati, 2022). The indicators used to measure work motivation are (1) the need for achievement, (2) the need for power, and (3) the need for affiliation (Sunyoto, 2015). Supported by previous research by (Muna & Isnowati, 2022) and Ardiyanti et al., (2023) work motivation affects employee performance. However, in contrast to (Dahman et al., 2023) work motivation does not have a negative and significant effect on employee performance. The inconsistency of these results requires further testing related to these variables.

The form of attention given by the company to its employees such as the company pays attention to the rights of its employees, pays attention to the needs of employees, and provides compensation such as salaries, incentives, and various benefits (Jufrizen, 2016). High job satisfaction indicates that an organization has managed employee needs well through effective management (Akbar et al., 2016). If these rights are given by the company to match the expectations of employees who have worked optimally in the company, employees feel fasting for the work that has been done (Jufrizen, 2016). Therefore, this study makes job satisfaction a mediating variable.

Employee job satisfaction can be obtained from several factors. Work-life balance, organizational culture, and leadership style are considered to be some of the causes of employee job satisfaction (Darmawan et al., 2020). Another opinion reveals that the factors that affect employee job satisfaction include the work environment and motivation (Wuwungan & Taroreh, 2017). From the factors mentioned above, researchers want to re-examine the factors of leadership style and work motivation. There is evidence from research conducted by (Liana, 2020) and (Yuliana et al., 2020) which corroborates that leadership style affects job satisfaction. (Kartika & Kaihatu, 2010) and (Saputra & Andani, 2021) also succeeded in proving that motivation affects job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction according to (Hasibuan, 2008), is an emotional attitude that explains where someone likes their job, where this attitude can be seen from work morale, achievement and discipline. Another definition of job satisfaction is an individual thing, the more aspects of the job that match individual desires, the higher the level of satisfaction felt, and vice versa (Noor & Agustina, 2019). In

addition, according to (Wani et al., 2018) job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards his job such as a positive emotional condition of someone who feels comfortable and has a level of loyalty in his job, so that at work the person gets job satisfaction following what is desired for the creation of quality work in the organization. Indicators of job satisfaction include: (1) liking his job, (2) loving his job, (3) work morale, (4) discipline, and (5) work performance (Hasibuan, 2008). Supported by previous research that job satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of leadership style on employee performance by (Sugiono et al., 2021). Artana & Mujiati, (2022) prove that job satisfaction is able to mediate work motivation on employee performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Employee Performance

Employee performance is a person's ability to carry out their duties and responsibilities in accordance with the standards set by the company. According to Armstrong and Baron (2018), employee performance can be measured through several aspects, such as productivity, work quality, initiative, attendance, and work attitude. Meanwhile, according to Dessler (2017), employee performance can also be seen from the point of view of the results achieved, the processes carried out, and the behavior shown. Good employee performance is very important for the success of the company. This is because good employee performance can increase the productivity, efficiency, and quality of the company's work. Conversely, poor employee performance can cause losses to the company, such as decreased productivity, low work quality, and higher costs.

B. Leadership Style

Leadership is the ability to influence others to achieve goals with enthusiasm (Davis et al., 1995). (J. Gibson, 1982) explains that leadership is a narrower concept than management. How a leader's efforts to influence others or so that the material follows what is ordered will depend on the leadership style used. Meanwhile, according to (Davis et al., 1995), leadership style is the leader's overall pattern of action as perceived by his employees. Leadership is the process of persuading others to comprehend and agree on what needs to be done and how the work is done successfully, as well as the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to reach common goals (Yukl, 2013). Effective leaders who use various leadership styles must first grasp who their subordinates are, their subordinates' strengths and shortcomings, and how to use subordinates' strengths to compensate for their deficiencies.

C. Work Motivation

According to the American Encyclopedia in (Hasibuan, 2008), motivation is a propensity in a person that arouses support and leads his actions. Motivation encompasses biological and emotional demands that can only be inferred from human behavior observations. G.R. Terry (Hasibuan, 2008). Suggestions that motivation is a desire within a person that stimulates him to perform. Motivation, according to Prof. PF. Drucker (in Anoraga, 2006), serves as a motivator for one's will and desire. And it is for this reason that they strive to integrate themselves and the company in order to play a

positive role. Motivation is important since it is what drives, channels, and supports human activity, so that they want to work hard and enthusiastically to achieve optimal results. Motivation is increasingly important because managers distribute work to their subordinates to be done properly and integrated into the desired goals (Hasibuan, 2008).

D. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to how employees feel about their employment and various elements of their jobs. It is a development of what individuals enjoy and dislike about their employment (satisfaction and unhappiness) (Spector, 1997). According to (J. L. Gibson et al., 1994) employment satisfaction is a positive attitude toward components of one's employment that develops over time. The employee's attitude stems from his view of his work. Wages, advancement possibilities, and coworkers are all factors that contribute to job satisfaction. This is emphasized by (Wagner & Hollenbeck, 2010) who quoted Locke's expression that job

satisfaction is: "a pleasurable feeling that results from the perception that one's job fulfills or allows for the fulfillment of one's important job values".

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The quantitative technique is used in this study. Quantitative research collects numerical data and uses statistical analysis to understand phenomena. Creswell (2014). This is causal associative study, which investigates the link between one or two additional variables (Sugiyono, 2014). The Slovin method was used to calculate the number of samples, and the samples were gathered using a proportionate random sampling technique, with 171 workers of PT Artefak Arkindo participating. A questionnaire on a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was used to collect data. The study data were analyzed using the Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) using smart PLS 3.0.

IV. RESULTS

Table 1. Panel Data Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Hubungan Antar Variabel	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Leadership Style -> Employee Performance	0,187	1,532	0,126
Leadership Style -> Job Satisfaction	0,444	4,627	0,000
Work Motivation -> Employee Performance	0,228	2,814	0,005
Work Motivation -> Job Satisfaction	0,480	5,475	0,000
Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0,527	4,199	0,000
Leadership Style -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0,234	2,845	0,005
Work Motivation -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0,253	3,629	0,000

Sources: Research Data, 2023

Based on the table above, the relationship between variables (hypothesis test results) can be explained as follows:

- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.187 and a P value of $0.05 < 0.126$ So that the first hypothesis (H1) is rejected.
- Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.228 and a P value of $0.05 < 0.005$ so the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.
- Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.527 and a P value of $0.05 < 0.000$ So the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted.
- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with a coefficient value of 0.444 and a P value of $0.05 < 0.000$ So the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted.
- Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction with a coefficient value of 0.480 and a P value of $0.05 < 0.000$ So the fifth hypothesis (H5) is accepted.
- The role of job satisfaction can mediate the positive effect of leadership style on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.234 and a P value of $0.05 < 0.005$. So that the sixth hypothesis (H6) is accepted.

- The role of job satisfaction can mediate the positive effect of work motivation on employee performance with a coefficient value of 0.253 and a P-Value of $0.05 < 0.000$. So that the seventh hypothesis (H7) is accepted.

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance

Based on Table 1, the results show that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo, so the first hypothesis (H1) is rejected. This means that the leadership style of a leader does not affect the work results that will be obtained by employees. This could be due to a number of factors that are complex and can affect these results. One of the main factors is the fit between the applied leadership style and the characteristics or needs of the team or individuals being led. The leadership style adopted may not fit the working dynamics of a particular team or organizational environment.

B. The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

Based on table 1, the results show that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo, so the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted. This means that motivation acts as an internal driver that encourages individuals to act, try, and perform better. When

an employee feels motivated, several important things happen that contribute to improved performance. Work motivation directs employees' attention to the goals to be achieved. Motivated employees have a clear view of what they want to achieve, both in terms of daily tasks and long-term targets.

C. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Based on table 1, the results show that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo, so the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted. Job satisfaction can be a factor that increases employee motivation, commitment, and engagement in their work, which in turn improves their performance. When employees feel satisfied with their jobs, they tend to have an internal drive to do a good job. They are more likely to experience intrinsic motivation, where the satisfaction of the completed task becomes their primary driver. Job satisfaction can also result in a deeper sense of emotional engagement with work, making employees feel more connected to the goals and values of the organization.

D. The Effect of Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

Based on the findings in Table 1, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted: leadership style has a positive and substantial influence on work satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo. This suggests that a firm leader's more suitable leadership style will boost employee work satisfaction. A leadership style that empowers and empowers individuals to make decisions and complete tasks is also significant in enhancing job satisfaction. Leaders instill a sense of ownership and responsibility in their workers by allowing them to take an active role in their job. Such changes can promote work satisfaction and loyalty to the business by providing a sense of accomplishment and skill advancement.

E. The Effect of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Based on Table 1, the results show that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo, so the fifth hypothesis (H5) is accepted. This means that the higher work motivation of employees will increase their job satisfaction. Work motivation includes various factors, such as the desire to achieve, a sense of responsibility for work, a sense of pride in the contributions made, and a feeling of being recognized for good performance. When employees feel that their work has meaning and a meaningful purpose, they will be more motivated to give their best. When an employee feels motivated, they tend to be more focused and dedicated to their work. They will look for ways to overcome challenges and improve their skills, thus improving the quality of work and achieving better results.

F. The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction on the Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

Based on table 1, the results show that the effect of leadership style on employee performance mediated by job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on PT Artefak Arkindo, so the sixth hypothesis (H6) is accepted. An effective leadership style creates a positive work environment, where superiors provide support, clear direction, and participation opportunities. This creates a feeling among employees that they are valued and cared for

in their roles. Job satisfaction, as a mediator in the relationship between leadership style and employee performance, acts as an important bridge in connecting the two. When employees are satisfied with their jobs, it reflects their positive perceptions of the work environment and interactions with superiors. This job satisfaction provides strong intrinsic motivation, encouraging employees to put more effort and dedication into their tasks.

G. The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction on the Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

Table 1 shows that the influence of leadership style on employee performance as mediated by job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on PT Artefak Arkindo, indicating that the seventh hypothesis (H7) is validated. Work motivation is an internal force that motivates employees to strive for certain goals. People are more eager, proactive, and devoted to their occupations when they are inspired. Job satisfaction connects job motivation to employee performance. Employee satisfaction shows the congruence between expectations and reality in the workplace. This job pleasure delivers favorable sentiments, rewards, and psychological fulfillment, which enhances the work drive. Employee performance is influenced by job satisfaction in a variety of ways. When employees are satisfied with their jobs, they are more likely to have high energy levels and strong intrinsic motivation to strive for good results.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Leadership style has an insignificant effect on employee performance at PT Artefak Arkindo. A good leadership style creates a productive and supportive work environment. Leaders who are able to communicate well, listen, and provide constructive feedback, help employees understand job goals and expectations better.

Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Artefak Arkindo. This means that when employees feel motivated, they tend to have high levels of energy, focus, and commitment to their tasks.

Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT Artefak Arkindo. This means that job satisfaction provides intrinsic motivation, namely motivation that comes from within the individual. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more motivated to try to achieve good results.

Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at PT Artefak Arkindo. This means that a leadership style that provides appropriate direction to employees encourages them to seek self-development opportunities and take responsibility for their work. Support and guidance from leaders help employees overcome obstacles in their career development

Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on career development at PT Artefak Arkindo. This means that motivated employees tend to be more proactive in seeking training, learning, and taking greater responsibility for achieving their career goals. Strong work motivation also helps create a positive attitude towards learning and self-

development. With high motivation, employees feel more energized and committed to achieving growth and success in their careers.

Job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of leadership style on employee performance at PT Artefak Arkindo. An effective leadership style creates conditions that support employees to feel satisfied in their work. Job satisfaction, in turn, affects employees' level of motivation, commitment, and energy in carrying out their tasks, which ultimately affects their performance.

Job satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of work motivation on employee performance at PT Artefak Arkindo. That is, work motivation affects the extent to which a person is motivated to work hard and make maximum contributions in their work. On the other hand, job satisfaction reflects the extent to which employees feel satisfied with various aspects of their work.

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